

Demystifying Machine Learning: Applications in African Environmental Science and Engineering

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Abstract:

This article delves into the transformative role of Machine Learning (ML) in Environmental Science and Engineering (ESE), illustrating its broad applications across diverse environmental issues and its potential to enhance decision-making and operational efficiency. It emphasizes the integration of ML techniques such as regression analysis, anomaly detection, and deep learning to address complex challenges in climate change, energy management, water resource management, and more. The document particularly focuses on the adaptation and challenges of ML in the African context, highlighting barriers such as infrastructure limitations and data scarcity, while

proposing innovative solutions like cloud computing and lightweight models. Practical use cases in meteorology, energy optimization, and water management underscore the practical impacts of ML, showing significant advancements in forecasting, resource management, and system optimization. The article also discusses methodological considerations necessary for effective ML application in ESE, including model selection and rigorous benchmarking. Ultimately, it provides a comprehensive overview of current capabilities, challenges, and future directions for ML in environmental science, advocating for continued innovation and tailored solutions to meet the unique needs of different regions, particularly Africa.

Keywords: *Machine Learning, Environmental Science and Engineering, Climate Change, Data Analysis, Sustainable Solutions.*

Introduction

Data science is experiencing a global paradigm shift, with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) redefining our interactions with and understanding of data (Borenstein & Howard, 2021; Carlos J. Costa & Manuela Aparicio, 2023). Covering a wide range of methodologies from basic database management to advanced analytics, data science integrates techniques from statistics, computer science, and information theory to extract

insights from both structured and unstructured data (Sarker, 2021).

AI, aiming to replicate human cognitive functions through machines, involves sophisticated tasks such as visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, and language translation (Carlos J Costa & Manuela Aparicio, 2023). Machine Learning, as an integral part of AI, concentrates on crafting algorithms that allow models to autonomously learn and make inferences from data. Machine Learning, a crucial subset of AI, focuses on developing

algorithms that enable models to learn from data independently. This capability is pivotal across various sectors including Environmental Science and Engineering (ESE), healthcare, and finance, driving significant advancements and

innovations.(V. De Faria, A. De Queiroz, L. Lima, J. Lima, & B. Da Silva, 2022; V. A. D. de Faria, A. R. de Queiroz, L. M. Lima, J. W. M. Lima, & B. C. da Silva, 2022; Zhong et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Overlaps and Distinctions in the Relationships Between AI, Machine Learning, and Statistics

Source: Hsieh, 2022

The use of Machine Learning (ML) in Environmental Science and Engineering (ESE) is driven by human-induced disturbances and climate stressors, which are harming the planet's health. These factors have changed our environments and ecosystems, leading to environmental degradation issues such as biodiversity loss, increased CO2 levels, oceanic plastic pollution, water resource scarcity, and deforestation (Kondo & Diwani, 2023; Trenberth, 2018). As humanity contends with the most significant challenge to date, Africa, in particular, has been disproportionately impacted by these environmental stressors (Dabelko & Conca, 2019; Palanichamy, Kargar, & Zolfagharinia, 2021).

Machine Learning in Environmental Science and Engineering

ML has demonstrated its adaptability across fields leveraging its capabilities in image classification (e.g., tumor detection in medical scans) (Carlos J. Costa & Manuela Aparicio, 2023). Its current expansion into data-centric disciplines like Earth System Science (ESS) has shifted towards utilizing historical data and

regression analyses to decipher complex patterns. This has proved useful in improving decision-making processes, especially in environmental forecasting and climate pattern analysis (Kondo & Diwani, 2023).

Advancements in remote sensing and cloud computing have greatly enhanced access to critical climate and hydrological data in Environmental Science and Engineering (ESE). This influx of high-dimensional data provides a robust foundation for training sophisticated AI models. Historically, the application of ML in ESE was confined to straightforward tasks like image classification and language translation. With the advent of big data, however, ML applications have broadened significantly, introducing both new challenges and opportunities (Carlos J. Costa & Manuela Aparicio, 2023). In this expanded context, a wide range of stakeholders, from tech companies to government agencies, utilize regression analysis to predict environmental trends and analyze climate patterns.

Global Trends and Practices

In the evolving landscape of ESE, the advent of Machine Learning and Deep Learning methodologies has transformed the way researchers address critical environmental challenges. These technologies have enhanced data analysis, prediction, and decision-making capabilities, leading to a deeper understanding of complex environmental systems and more effective interventions (Miller, Gray, & Bruning, 2020). Compared to global trends, the African continent exhibits a slower pace of ML adoption, an indication of existing barriers to access, such as limited infrastructure, data scarcity, and a lack of technical expertise. However, there are opportunities for the African ESE community to address these systemic challenges and leapfrog into innovative research areas:

- **Adoption of Lightweight Models:** Utilizing soft computing and lightweight algorithms, such as MobileNets, offers a practical solution to circumvent the constraints imposed by expensive hardware requirements. These models are less resource-intensive and can be effectively deployed on lower-specification equipment (Zhong et al., 2021).
- **Cloud Computing:** Cloud platforms can significantly reduce the need for advanced local infrastructure by providing scalable computing resources. This approach allows researchers to access state-of-the-art processing capabilities without substantial upfront investment.
- **Remote Sensing and Satellite Technology:** Satellite sensors and remote sensing technologies are critical in gathering extensive environmental data. These tools can help overcome the challenge of data scarcity by providing accurate, high-resolution environmental monitoring across vast and hard-to-reach areas (Chawla, Karthikeyan, & Mishra, 2020).
- **Utilization of Large Language Models (LLMs):** The advent of LLMs, like OpenAI's models, and tools such as GitHub Copilot, has democratized access to advanced

coding assistance. These innovations reduce the need for deep programming expertise, enabling more researchers to implement complex ML and DL solutions (Kazemitabaar et al., 2024).

Machine Learning Categories and Techniques

Machine learning algorithms are categorized into Supervised, Unsupervised, Semi-supervised, and Reinforcement learning. Each category serves distinct purposes and is chosen based on the specific environmental issue being addressed and the characteristics of the data. The diverse range of fields within ESE, presents numerous opportunities to apply these ML methods to complex environmental problems.

Supervised learning algorithms are used to map inputs to outputs, using training sets composed of features (inputs) and labels (outputs)—independent and dependent variables, respectively. These labels in supervised tasks may be discrete for classification problems or continuous for regression tasks aimed at quantitative predictions (Maganathan, Senthilkumar, & Balakrishnan, 2020).

Unsupervised learning, in contrast, works with unlabeled data to independently discover patterns and features. While it is not aimed at specific prediction tasks, it is crucial for uncovering hidden data structures, useful in clustering, dimension reduction, and anomaly detection (X. Liu, Lu, Zhang, Liu, & Jiang, 2022). In Environmental Chemistry, for example, it helps identify unknown pollutants, and in Geosciences, it aids in classifying soil types or mineral deposits from spectral data without explicit labels.

Semi-supervised learning combines elements of both supervised and unsupervised learning, using both labeled and unlabeled data (Hernandez-Matheus et al., 2022). This approach is particularly effective when labeled data are scarce but necessary, as in enhancing weather prediction models with a mix of historical and real-time sensor data, or in Ecology, where it integrates sparse biological

data with extensive environmental records to analyze ecosystem dynamics.

Reinforcement learning involves learning through trial and error, guided by rewards and penalties (L. Yu et al., 2019). It is ideal for tasks that require sophisticated decision-making, such as optimizing resource allocation in smart cities or automating waste management systems to maximize outcomes over time automating waste management systems, where the objective is to maximize outcomes over time.

In reality, while ML techniques are categorized for easier understanding, many of these techniques overlap in their applications and effectiveness across different types of data and environmental issues. ESE as a research field, is inherently complex as it involves the study of large, multidimensional natural systems that are difficult to adequately characterize (Miller et al., 2020). Consequently, this classification exercise will be neither clean nor exhaustive.

Table 1. Overview of Classical Machine Learning Techniques in Environmental Science and Engineering Applications

Technique	Application in ESE	Description
Regression Analysis	Modeling & Forecasting	Predicts continuous outcomes based on predictor variables, used for trend analysis, time series prediction, and quantitative data modeling.
Classification Analysis	Categorization	Predicts discrete outputs, crucial for categorizing environmental elements like water quality, land cover types. Extends to binary, multiclass, and multi-label classifications.
Anomaly Detection	Risk Mitigation	Identifies unusual patterns that may indicate environmental threats, crucial for preemptive measures.
Dimensionality Reduction	Data Simplification	Reduces the number of data dimensions to simplify models, enhance interpretability, and reduce computational demands.
Feature Selection	Model Optimization	Involves selecting the most relevant features from the dataset to improve model performance and reduce complexity.
Feature Extraction	New Feature Creation	Transforms original data into a new set of features, capturing essential information in a more compact form for better insights.
Cluster Analysis	Data Categorization	Automatically groups data into clusters based on similarities, used to analyze patterns in climate data or cluster species based on environmental conditions.
Material Discovery	Innovation in Materials	Leverages ML to predict properties of novel materials for environmental applications, such as catalysts or adsorbents.
Principal Component Analysis	Data Reduction & Interpretation	Reduces the dimensionality of large datasets, increasing interpretability while minimizing information loss. Useful where many variables are correlated, helping to highlight the most significant patterns and trends.
Correlation Analysis	Variable Relationship Analysis	Assesses the strength and direction of relationships between environmental variables. Helps understanding complex interdependencies in ecological data.

Practical Use Cases for Machine Learning in ESE

Over the last decade, machine learning (ML) has revolutionized Environmental and Sustainable Energy (ESE) initiatives by enhancing efficiency, sustainability, and decision-making. Its applications range from optimizing water resources to integrating renewable energy and advancing waste management. The following

examples showcase how ML not only addresses current environmental challenges, but also offers scalable solutions applicable to ESE efforts across Africa.

Climate Change

Recent years have seen a notable pivot toward employing Machine Learning (ML) to enhance human capabilities in developing effective strategies against climate change. This

application is crucial for addressing environmental challenges that span local to global scales and temporal ranges from immediate to multi-century timelines (Miller et al., 2020). The routes to mitigate climate change effects are complex and filled with implementation hurdles, ML faces its own unique challenges in this domain. Nonlinear ML algorithms, which require large amounts of data to be effective, often struggle in climate science due to the extended timescales involved that restrict the availability of robust datasets. Moreover, the common practice of aggregating daily climate observations to create datasets tends to oversimplify the intricate relationships between predictive variables and outcomes. This simplification, resulting from the central limit theorem, reduces the effectiveness of ML's nonlinear analytical capabilities (Hsieh, 2022; Yuval & Hsieh, 2002).

Despite these obstacles, the scientific community is actively developing strategies to address the issue of limited observational data, which has impeded the use of ML in climate science. One effective approach is transfer learning, where ML algorithms trained on large datasets are adapted to address different problems with smaller datasets (Hsieh, 2022). An example of this is the work by Ham et al. (2019), who used a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to learn patterns from the extensive CMIP5 climate model data, which included 2,961 months of outputs (Ham, Kim, & Luo, 2019). They then refined the model using an additional 103 months of reanalysis data, enhancing its predictive accuracy for the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) beyond traditional dynamical models. The same concept can be applied in the African context, where data is often aggregated and sparse, making training robust Deep Learning models from scratch impractical. Taking the example of Ham et al. (2019), researchers can leverage pre-trained models developed on global climate datasets, such as those from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), effectively bypassing the initial data-intensive training phase. These models, initially designed to understand large-scale climate phenomena, can be fine-tuned with

local data to forecast regional weather patterns more effectively.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have achieved significant success in meteorology, especially in developing Early Warning Systems for predicting droughts and floods. The strength of CNNs lies in their ability to process complex atmospheric phenomena via 2D imagery, making them exceptionally suitable for these applications. For example, Liu et al. (2016) applied CNNs to evaluate the likelihood of three types of extreme weather events—tropical cyclones, atmospheric rivers, and weather fronts—using two-dimensional representations of atmospheric variables (Y. Liu et al., 2016). Similarly, Lagerquist et al. (2019) employed CNN models to identify synoptic-scale weather fronts, effectively differentiating between cold fronts, warm fronts, and no-front scenarios (Lagerquist, McGovern, & Gagne II, 2019). Additionally, Cintineo et al. (2020) developed a CNN-based system for predicting intense convection using data from geostationary satellites (Cintineo et al., 2020). Beyond meteorology, CNN architectures like U-net have found varied application within the environmental sciences domain, like Land Cover Classification (Ulmas & Liiv, 2020), Vegetation Analysis (Choi, Lee, Kang, Choi, & Choi, 2020; Wei, Zhang, Wang, Wang, & Xu, 2019), Waterbodies Detection, Soil Moisture Estimation (Habiboullah & Louly, 2023) and Pollution Monitoring, demonstrating its versatility and effectiveness.

In several African countries, ML techniques are being employed to enhance seasonal climate forecasting. The South African Weather Service (SAWS) integrates ML techniques to refine their weather prediction models. Furthermore collaborative programmes like the African SWIFT (Science for Weather Information and Forecasting Techniques) have employed ML techniques to enhance seasonal climate forecasting in parts of East and West Africa (Ulmas & Liiv, 2020). African ESE Researchers can use resources like USAID's Famine Early Warning Systems Network (FEWS NET) use ML to analyze satellite data and other climate indicators to predict droughts months in

advance, providing valuable lead time for mitigation efforts. Various international collaborations, such as those facilitated by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and African Union, support the development of ML capabilities in Africa. These include WMO's Severe Weather Forecasting Demonstration Project (SWFDP), African SWIFT (Science for Weather Information and Forecasting Techniques) and The African Union's Africa Regional Data Cube (ARDC).

Energy

Energy consumption and its production methods are crucial to societal and environmental health (Miller et al., 2020). Africa faces significant energy challenges, with a pressing need for reliable and sustainable power amid rising demands. The continent's energy infrastructure, particularly its outdated electrical grids, struggles with inefficiencies and frequent power outages, hindering economic growth. Machine learning offers transformative solutions by optimizing grid operations and integrating renewable energies effectively. The following section will demonstrate how machine learning grid optimization and energy management can make tangible differences in improving grid reliability and efficiency.

Grid Optimization

Modernizing and optimizing the energy grid is essential for African countries aiming to meet sustainability goals and enhance infrastructure efficiency. The grid, crucial for delivering reliable electricity to homes, businesses, and industries, supports economic growth, technological progress, and improved living standards (Fasogbon & Shaibu, 2023). However, traditional grids face numerous inefficiency challenges, including the mismatching of energy demand and supply, which can destabilize operations (W. Ahmed et al., 2020). Optimization of the energy grid is vital to accommodate rising demands and maintain stability amidst fluctuating generation and changing demand profiles. This involves real-time balancing of generation against load to

prevent blackouts or brownouts that disrupt essential services and daily activities (Byrne, Nguyen, Copp, Chalamala, & Gyuk, 2018). This reduces costs by enhancing load balancing and reducing transmission losses, leading to lower energy prices for consumers and businesses. It reduces reliance on fossil fuels and associated greenhouse gas emissions, aligning with global sustainability efforts.

Energy grid optimization employs advanced technologies and techniques to enhance the efficiency of energy generation, transmission, and distribution, while also reducing costs and environmental impacts. Machine learning (ML) algorithms play a crucial role in this process by analyzing vast amounts of data from diverse sources such as smart meters, weather sensors, and energy markets, to predict energy demand, optimize energy generation and distribution, and control energy consumption in real-time. As a result, operators can not only minimize operational costs but also lessen the environmental footprint of energy production and consumption (Fasogbon & Shaibu, 2023).

In recent years, there has been a surge in the use of more advanced machine learning techniques for energy grid optimization:

Demand Response

Demand response programs are crucial for balancing energy supply with fluctuating consumer demands, particularly during peak periods. Machine learning plays a pivotal role by analyzing historical and real-time data to predict peak demand times. Through predictive analytics, energy providers can incentivize or adjust consumer behavior to either reduce or shift their energy usage, contributing to grid stability and efficiency.

Lu employed Q-learning, a type of reinforcement learning, in demand response strategies is to dynamically adjust electricity prices to maintain balance between demand and supply in the smart grid (Lu, Hong, & Zhang, 2018). Q-learning models this pricing challenge as a discrete finite Markov decision process (MDP), optimizing electricity prices in real-time to reflect shifting conditions (Reka, Venugopal,

Alhelou, Siano, & Golshan, 2021). This algorithm successfully identified the optimal actions in various states based on rewards, and was effectively used to develop dynamic pricing strategies that adapt to real-time fluctuations in electricity demand and supply (Lu et al., 2018).

Deep Neural Networks (DNN) and Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) have also been used to forecast electricity prices and load demands under uncertain conditions for effective demand response management (Reka et al., 2021). DNNs excel in modeling complex patterns within large datasets, making them ideal for the fluctuating nature of electricity markets. Deep Q-Learning (DQN) and Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) techniques enhance traditional reinforcement learning by incorporating deep learning architectures (Reka et al., 2021).

Load Forecasting

Accurate load forecasting facilitates efficient power generation and distribution planning, reducing energy waste and enhancing reliability. By improving forecast accuracy, utilities can lower the risk of outages and better integrate renewable energy sources by precisely predicting the availability of wind and solar power. This precision also helps in minimizing costs related to over- and under-contracts on balancing markets, boosts power market efficiency, and deepens understanding of monitored system dynamics (Fasogbon & Shaibu, 2023). Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) are commonly used to enhance the accuracy of demand forecasting in distribution networks, including those for energy, telecommunications, and transportation.

Bianchi (2018) performs a comparative study of different classes of state-of-the-art RNNs, including Echo State Networks, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), and Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) for Short Term Load Forecasting (STLF), particularly focusing on their ability to handle real-valued time series data which is crucial for predicting demand and consumption in energy supply networks (Bianchi, Maiorino, Kampffmeyer, Rizzi, & Jenssen, 2017). The study uses historical power usage data, along with weather patterns and economic indicators,

to forecast future energy demands. Findings indicate that no single RNN model consistently excels across all forecasting tasks; instead, the performance of each RNN type varies based on the specific prediction task, highlighting the need for customized training strategies and configurations.

Fault Detection and Identification

Fault detection in energy systems is crucial for ensuring reliability and safety. Machine learning techniques such as Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and Random Forests are employed to analyze sensor data across the grid to pinpoint anomalies that could indicate faults. These models are trained using historical data that include instances of both faults and normal operations, which helps them differentiate between typical fluctuations and genuine issues.

SVMs are particularly adept at classification tasks and are used to identify unusual patterns in voltage or current that may indicate equipment failures. They utilize both historical and real-time measurements as input, enhancing the effectiveness of the grid's protection control system (Hernandez-Matheus et al., 2022). On the other hand, Random Forests can process a large number of input variables and detect complex interactions that may signal potential failures. These systems provide real-time monitoring and fast response capabilities, minimizing downtime and preventing minor issues from escalating into major disruptions. Proactive fault detection not only improves grid reliability but also extends the lifespan of the infrastructure by addressing problems early. (Fasogbon & Shaibu, 2023).

Sapountzoglou et al. (2020) introduce a novel fault detection and diagnosis method for low voltage (LV) smart distribution grids using Gradient Boosting Trees (GBT) (Sapountzoglou, Lago, & Raison, 2020). This approach specifically targets high-impedance faults, which have been less covered in previous research. GBTs are favored for their ability to amalgamate multiple weak predictors into a robust predictive model, making them efficient and fast, suitable for real-time applications. The algorithm excels in detecting faults, particularly

in identifying the type of feeder and fault, including the challenging high-impedance faults. Its generalizability across different grid topologies was demonstrated with promising results in both the trained grid and other tested grids. The quick computation times of GBT make it well-suited for real-time fault diagnosis, crucial for reducing downtime and enhancing grid reliability.

Incentivization

Incentivization in energy management encourages prosumers, also known as Energy Districts (EDs), to adjust their energy usage during specific times for demand-side management. However, integrating renewable energy sources like wind and solar can cause fluctuations due to variable wind speeds and solar irradiance. Effective optimization requires precise system specifications, which must be updated when conditions change, such as variable energy supplies from renewables or shifting prosumer demands. Consequently, algorithms that cannot adapt to these variations are challenging to deploy and test in real-time.

Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) is a key optimization technique in smart grid energy management, particularly effective for addressing the unpredictability of renewable energy sources like wind and solar. GPR excels in predicting crucial performance indicators such as Prosumer Energy Surplus (PES), Prosumer Energy Cost (PEC), and Grid Revenue (GR), essential for optimizing grid operations. This advanced machine learning method is highly capable of managing complex, non-linear data, offering a robust response to the stochastic variability of renewable energy generation. By employing GPR, the accuracy and reliability of energy predictions are significantly improved, facilitating the development of adaptive service level agreements that enhance both economic and operational efficiencies of smart grids. This showcases how GPR adeptly tackles the complexities and challenges in modern energy systems (W. Ahmed et al., 2020).

Water Resources Management

The ramifications of climate change—such as rising temperatures, changing precipitation patterns, and more frequent extreme weather events like floods and droughts—significantly impact the predictability, quality, and availability of global water resources. In response, researchers are increasingly turning to machine learning (ML)-based decision support systems. These systems adeptly handle the complexities and uncertainties in water resource management, arising from both natural and human influences and the variability of the climate. Traditionally, water resource management relied on physical models using empirical equations to describe aquatic systems. However, ML models are now widely applied in various aspects of water resource management due to their adeptness at addressing complex water-related challenges (Maganathan et al., 2020).

Streamflow prediction

Streamflow forecasting in African catchments faces significant challenges due to the limitations of traditional models. Conceptual models like the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) simplify hydrological systems by dividing watersheds into individual components, using condensed equations, which often bypass intricate details and nonlinear interactions, compromising accuracy in complex watersheds (Doswell & Brooks, 2001; Paul et al., 2021; Trinh & Molkenhain, 2021). Physical-based models like HEC-HMS and MIKE SHE, on the other hand simulate hydrological processes using core equations (Brekke, Dettinger, Maurer, & Anderson, 2008; Mwale, Adeloye, & Rustum, 2014). They require exceptionally detailed data, and are resource-intensive as complex algorithms increase computational demands (Ikhwalu et al., 2022). Their many parameters can lead to uncertainties, hence their use in forecasting is often limited to smaller catchments (Moore & Bell, 2001; Todini, 1996).

Machine Learning (ML) models overcome the linearity constraints of traditional models through their nonlinear processing capabilities (Mwale et al., 2014). Their ability to approximate complex functions, leading to their adoption by leading agencies in developed economies for

streamflow forecasting, enhancing risk-informed basin services (Baker, Rajagopalan, & Wood, 2021). Recent advancements include the use of AI techniques such as classifiers, fuzzy logic, evolutionary computation, and wavelet conjunction for hydrological analyses (Nourani, Tahershamsi, Abbaszadeh, Shahrabi, & Hadavandi, 2014). Wu et al. (2005) applied two Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs) to predict watershed runoff and streamflow in North Carolina, using hourly precipitation and streamflow data. The models' performance was evaluated using the correlation coefficient (R), mean squared error (MSE), and relative error (RE), demonstrating their effectiveness in providing near-real-time forecasts in 15-minute increments (Wu, Han, Annambhotla, & Bryant, 2005). Sarkar and Kumar (2012) developed an event-based rainfall-runoff model for the Sarath gauging site, using streamflow as input and measuring error with R and RE (Sarkar & Kumar, 2012). Additionally, Ahmed and Sarma (2007) used an ARMA model, Thomas-Fiering model, and MLP to forecast monthly streamflow on the Pagladia River and another Brahmaputra tributary, assessing performance with MSE and RE. Their findings indicated that the MLP was particularly effective in generating synthetic streamflow series for the Pagladia River (J. A. Ahmed & Sarma, 2007).

Ground Water Quality Monitoring and Prediction

Groundwater Quality Assessment and Prediction is essential for protecting groundwater resources, especially in arid or semi-arid areas where surface water is scarce (Huang et al., 2023). Factors such as population growth, climate variability, mining, and excessive groundwater extraction have greatly increased the vulnerability of Africa's aquifers and groundwater systems to contamination and depletion (Adiat, Akeredolu, Akinlalu, & Olayanju, 2020). Common groundwater contaminants in many African countries include nitrate (NO₃⁻) from agriculture (Band et al., 2020), Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) (Banadkooki et al., 2020), and acid mine drainage containing dangerous substances like cyanide and mercury. The complexity of groundwater

systems makes accurate predictions of vulnerability challenging. Additionally, monitoring groundwater quality and quantity requires extensive and often expensive networks of monitoring wells, which can be technically demanding to establish and manage. This results in a significant lack of reliable data on groundwater levels and depletion rates, especially in rural or isolated areas.

Consuming water contaminated with nitrate poses significant health risks, including adult cancers, through both ingestion and dermal exposure (Ward et al., 2005; G. Yu et al., 2020). Traditional methods for assessing aquifer vulnerability often face challenges such as high computational demands, extensive data requirements, and difficulties in addressing the uncertainties of groundwater vulnerability. In response, Machine Learning (ML) techniques offer a valuable alternative, providing efficient and adaptable solutions. Approaches like Logistic Regression (Adiat et al., 2020), Data Clustering Analysis, and models like the Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS), Support Vector Machines (SVMs), and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models (Banadkooki et al., 2020) have demonstrated remarkable adaptability and rapid learning capabilities. These ML-based approaches circumvent the limitations of classical methods, enabling more effective and nuanced assessments of groundwater vulnerability.

Wastewater Treatment and Management

The rapid urbanization across Africa significantly raises the challenges and costs of wastewater management. Elevated levels of Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) in critical water bodies such as lakes and reservoirs, often surpass acceptable thresholds due to domestic sewage and industrial waste from facilities like abattoirs and manufacturers. These contaminants frequently enter water bodies without adequate treatment processes in place (Iloms, Ololade, Ogola, & Selvarajan, 2020). The resulting sludge from wastewater treatment operations poses both a challenge and an

opportunity, spotlighting the importance of effective sludge management which aims to minimize volume and mass, stabilize biodegradable substances, prevent secondary pollution, and repurpose materials for energy generation (Li et al., 2023). The following are examples of how ML has been used to tackle some common problems in WWTT:

Influent quality monitoring optimizes wastewater treatment by managing costs, preventing system overload, and facilitating long-term planning, and rapid emergency responses. Qin et al. (2012) developed a multi-sensor wastewater quality monitoring system to reduce costs associated with Hong Kong's Trade Effluent Surcharge (Chan, 2009; Tegizbekova, 2019). This system, used in a Chinese restaurant within a university campus, combined an UV/Vis spectrometer and a turbidimeter for precise measurement of Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), and Oil & Grease (O&G) levels. Integrated with an electrocoagulation–electroflotation (EC–EF) pilot plant, the system also used an Ensemble Machine Learning model with a Boosting-Iterative Predictor Weighting-Partial Least Squares (Boosting-IPW-PLS) algorithm to improve data accuracy and manage noise from sensor data integration, enhancing wastewater quality assessment (Qin, Gao, & Chen, 2012). This scalable ML approach offers a viable solution for developing countries to address water quality challenges, ensuring effective water treatment, compliance with standards, and resource management vital for sustainable development amid growing industrialization.

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) use activated sludge processes to remove key contaminants such as organic carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus. Each system may host diverse microbial communities, with thousands of species impacting the treatment effectiveness. The dynamic operations of WWTPs, characterized by variable and complex interactions among these microbes, pose a challenge in understanding their effect on system efficiency. ML techniques offer the ability to predict issues like sludge bulking and analyze the intricate relationships between microbial

activities and operational parameters, leveraging data sequencing and computational models for deep analysis without extensive calibration (Zhong et al., 2021).

Multivariate statistical methods like Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and hierarchical k-means clustering are essential for analyzing relationships between influential factors such as nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions and operational parameters like dissolved oxygen levels, nitrogen content, temperature, and water flow velocities. These techniques are instrumental in pinpointing the primary drivers of N₂O emissions and predicting key water quality metrics, including concentrations of total phosphorus, nitrogen, and total suspended solids (TSS) in WWTPs (X. Liu et al., 2022). Despite their utility, these approaches encounter challenges due to the inconsistent timing of data collection and the interdependence of variables, which contribute to temporal variations and instability in the quality of treated effluent.

To circumvent these challenges, advanced deep learning techniques, including Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), have been adopted. Hwangbo (2021) showed the efficacy of Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks in modeling and predicting N₂O emissions from WWTPs, outshining traditional Deep Neural Network (DNN) models with an R² value exceeding 0.94 (Hwangbo, Al, Chen, & Sin, 2021). This approach has also been applied to forecast municipal solid waste (MSW) generation rates using historical waste data combined with climatic and environmental variables. Notably, the multisite LSTM model significantly outperforms traditional models like the autoregressive integrated moving average model by an average of 85%, highlighting the potential of advanced machine learning techniques to manage the complex dynamics of wastewater treatment and waste generation (Cubillos, 2020).

Environment Monitoring and Conservation

Environmental Monitoring and Conservation is a domain where African ESE networks can utilize cutting-edge methodologies with relatively low barriers to entry. Earth observation satellites generate vast amounts of data daily at various temporal scales, which are highly suitable for Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms. These algorithms are exceptional at analyzing complex and diverse patterns in remote sensing data, including freely accessible satellite imagery. ML and DL excel in applications such as land cover mapping, environmental parameter retrieval, data fusion, downscaling, and prediction (Maganathan et al., 2020; Yuan et al., 2020).

Convolution Neural Networks (CNN), Deep Belief Network (DBN), Faster Region-based Convolutional Network (Faster R-CNN), Transfer Learning, Stacked auto encoder (SAE) and Long short-term memory (LSTM) are adept at processing and analyzing complex environmental data, facilitating tasks such as pattern recognition, temporal data analysis, and feature extraction from high-dimensional datasets. Moreover, tree-based supervised learning models like random forest algorithms, GBMs play a crucial role in EWM by providing robust mechanisms for making predictions and aiding in the development of decision support systems (Maganathan et al., 2020).

The Conditional Generative Adversarial Network (CGAN) has become a valuable tool in Environmental Sciences (ES), especially in atmospheric remote sensing. Leinonen et al. (2019) demonstrated its effectiveness by using CGAN to generate cloud structures on a 2D vertical plane along the satellite's tracking direction (Leinonen, Guillaume, & Yuan, 2019). Additionally, CGAN has been adopted as an innovative alternative to the U-net architecture for super-resolution tasks. For instance, Pashaei et al. (2020) used it to enhance the resolution of low-quality images taken by unmanned aircraft systems, converting them into high-definition images (Hsieh, 2022).

The prediction of wildfire risk has become increasingly critical in Africa, where the rising incidences and growing aridity attributed to

climate change have heightened the urgency for effective forecasting tools. Sayad et al. (2019) proposed an innovative approach for predicting wildfire occurrences, leveraging the capabilities of big data analytics, remote sensing technologies, and machine learning (ML) models, specifically Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Support Vector Machines (SVM) (Sayad, Mousannif, & Al Moatassime, 2019). These models demonstrated remarkable prediction accuracies, with ANN achieving 98.32% and SVM reaching 97.48%. Additionally, the utilization of wildfire data has further enhanced the capacity to predict alterations in air quality, employing advanced ML methodologies to provide more accurate forecasts of pollution levels (Sayad et al., 2019).

Selecting the Right Machine Learning Model

Selecting the appropriate machine learning (ML) model and dataset is fundamental in shaping the research trajectory and outcomes in Environmental Science and Engineering (ESE). This process involves matching the dataset characteristics, whether structured, like meteorological readings, or unstructured, like satellite imagery, with suitable ML models to ensure effective, real-world application.

The variety of data within ESE demands a calculated approach to selecting the appropriate ML model. For structured data, such as streamflow or temperature readings, traditional ML models like linear regression, decision trees, and support vector machines (SVMs) are typically chosen for their clarity and efficiency, particularly with smaller datasets. On the other hand, unstructured data requires more complex approaches like CNNs for tasks like monitoring satellite imagery due to their ability to analyze visual inputs. Model choice also depends on the size and complexity of the dataset. For instance, simple models like k-nearest neighbors (kNN) are suitable for smaller datasets, offering a computationally efficient and easily interpretable solution, perfect for applications like wildlife tracking.

Deep learning models, such as recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and convolutional neural networks (CNNs), play a crucial role in analyzing large-scale environmental data, adept at revealing patterns within high-dimensional datasets. However, a significant challenge in applying machine learning (ML) in Environmental Science and Engineering (ESE)

is balancing model complexity with interpretability. While more complex models offer superior predictive capabilities, simpler models provide greater transparency. This transparency is essential in ESE, where understanding the rationale behind predictions is often as important as the predictions' accuracy itself.

Figure 210 A categorized visual map of core techniques and methodologies in Machine Learning

Benchmarking and Testing

Benchmarking and testing machine learning models are essential for ensuring robustness and reproducibility of research. The methodology

outlined below provides a structured approach for evaluating ML models, focusing on setting standards for reproducibility, facilitating fair comparisons across different models or

architectures, and maintaining transparency throughout the research process

Consistency and Reproducibility

Consistent data usage across training, validation, and testing phases is essential. This uniformity allows direct, fair comparisons of different models or architectures under identical conditions. Rigorously document any data-specific manipulations to maintain reproducibility.

Comprehensive Documentation and Transparency

Provide complete, open-source accessible source code that covers all computational steps from data processing to model evaluation. This practice not only facilitates collaboration but also enhances the reproducibility of the research. Ensure the code is well-documented, adheres to coding standards, and includes a detailed README file to assist other researchers in understanding and using your methodologies.

Model Evaluation and Validation

After finalizing model architecture and hyperparameters, models should be retrained using the combined training and validation datasets. Subsequent performance evaluation on a test set offers a thorough assessment of the model's effectiveness. Utilize existing tools and software for benchmarking to establish baseline comparisons, which are critical for evaluating enhancements or the need for further model refinement.

Data Accessibility

In cases where direct data sharing is impractical, it is imperative to provide comprehensive access methods. This includes sharing anonymized datasets, offering detailed instructions for data reconstruction, or providing the necessary scripts for data generation. Such transparency supports external validation and replication of results, adhering to principles of open science.

Detailed Hyperparameter and Model Configuration Sharing

Record and disseminate all tested hyperparameters and the configurations that yielded the best results. This includes sharing trained model weights and necessary reconstruction codes, which are essential for ensuring that the research can be accurately replicated and further built upon.

Robust Evaluation Metrics

Employ a set of robust metrics designed to evaluate the model performance effectively. Metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and the area under the ROC curve (AUC) should be selected based on their relevance to the specific challenges and objectives of materials informatics. These metrics provide a comprehensive view of model performance and are crucial for comparative analysis.

Addressing Class Imbalance

Implement techniques to manage class imbalance, such as synthetic data generation or adaptive sampling methods. Ensuring balanced class representation during model training is crucial for avoiding biased performance evaluations and enhancing the model's applicability to real-world scenarios.

Integrating these standards into the procedures described in your work not only enhances the robustness of the benchmarking process but also ensures that the evaluations are fair, transparent, and replicable. This synthesis of accepted practices with your specified methodologies establishes a solid foundation for advancing machine learning applications in environmental science.

Conclusion

As the African ESE community adopts machine learning (ML) practices, it is important to recognize that, on a global scale, the integration of these technologies is still evolving. This reflects a broader trend where ESE is progressively bridging the gap between the established methods of knowledge engineering and the innovative approaches of ML within the field of Environmental Science and Engineering.

As African ESE communities endeavor to adopt machine learning (ML) technologies, it is crucial to address this developmental lag promptly to prevent the widening of knowledge gaps to unsustainable levels. Active participation in the ML revolution is essential for African ESE, as closing this gap not only addresses technical challenges but also represents a shift toward more integrative, accurate, and relevant models within ESE. The successful integration of ML with ESE is expected to significantly enhance our understanding and management of environmental challenges by capitalizing on the nuanced understanding and contextual precision of human expertise alongside the dynamic, scalable capabilities of ML technologies.

This fusion of structured, expert knowledge with advanced data-processing techniques is a crucial step forward, poised to transform problem-solving methodologies in the field. However, this expansion comes with its own set of challenges:

- The current abundance of data has enabled the adoption of sophisticated ML algorithms like deep neural networks. These powerful tools, though effective, often lack transparency in their decision-making processes, emphasizing the need for advancements in model interpretability to ensure that ML predictions align with core ESE principles.
- Additionally, the integration of scientific laws—such as those from physics and chemistry—into neural network models could significantly enhance their predictive power and relevance to ESE. Furthermore, conducting Applicability Domain (AD) analysis post-model development is vital to ascertain the operational boundaries and reliability of models across diverse environments. This practice, though common in fields like developing quantitative structure-activity relationships (QSARs), is underutilized in ESE, representing a potential area for growth.

These aspects underscore the critical research opportunities at the intersection of ESE and ML, demanding a collaborative partnership between field practitioners and ML researchers. The unique perspectives and insights from ESE

professionals are invaluable for refining ML methodologies and addressing the practical challenges encountered in the field, thus ensuring a more effective and comprehensive approach to environmental science and engineering."

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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